

INTERFACIAL REACTIONS IN Al_3Ti COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This work involved a study of the fabrication parameters and subsequent interfacial reactions in Al_3Ti composites. Al_3Ti based intermetallics were reinforced with two different filaments e.g. SCS-6 and SCS-6 coated with TiB_2 . Al_3Ti powder was produced by the comminution of melt spun ribbon. The fibers and the alloy powder were cold compacted, vacuum degassed, and canned. The composites were hot isostatically pressed (HIP). The microstructures of the composites were examined using optical and scanning electron microscopy. X-ray diffraction and Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS) were used to interrogate the chemistry of the composite. In addition, microhardness tests were employed to obtain mechanical property measurements from the fiber matrix interphase region. The reaction between the matrix and the fiber was examined. The presence of residual amounts of aluminum in the matrix dominated the resultant reactions which occurred.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Aluminides; Interface; Compatibility; Rapid Solidification

1. INTRODUCTION

Titanium trialuminides have mechanical and physical attributes that are attractive for aerospace applications. Al_3Ti has a high melting temperature ($1340^\circ C$), a low density (3.35 gcm^{-3}), and a specific elastic modulus ($50.7 \text{ MPam}^3/\text{kg}$) twice that of aluminum, titanium, or magnesium.(1) In addition, the high aluminum content of these intermetallics suggests that they

are inherently more resistant to oxidation than other titanium aluminides, viz., Ti_3Al and $TiAl$.(2) Unfortunately, trialuminides are brittle and lack appreciable ductility (less than one percent).

In order for trialuminides to be viable aircraft alloys, their ductility and fracture toughness must be enhanced. Research is currently in progress to improve the fracture toughness of these intermetallics through macro-alloying, micro-alloying, and rapid solidification.(3,4,5)

In order to promote slip, macroalloying with elements such as Cu, Mn, Cr, and Fe has been used to convert the DO_{22} BCT crystal structure of Al_3Ti to FCC $L1_2$. Microalloying with small amounts of boron has also been attempted; however, unlike nickel aluminides the ductility of Al_3Ti was not improved. HIP processed, rapidly solidified Al_3Ti plus copper did show superior crack resistance compared to cast material. This was attributed to its fine grain size and chemical homogeneity.(6) In addition, filamentary reinforced trialuminides are being considered as a means to improve fracture toughness. Critical in the development of these composites is the thermodynamic and mechanical compatibility of the fiber, matrix, and fiber/matrix interphase region.

Textron Specialty Materials produced two SiC fibers used in this study: SCS-6 and SCS-6 coated with TiB_2 . The SCS-6 fiber is a 140 μm diameter monofilament produced by chemical vapor deposition (CVD). It consists of a carbon core and radially oriented β -SiC. The surface of the fiber has a carbon rich layer. The high strength (72.5 MPa), high modulus (415 GPa), and low density (3.0 gcm^{-3}) of SCS-6 fibers make them attractive for use as reinforcing fibers.

The overall approach taken in this study was to enhance the toughness of the Al_3Ti matrix by use of Rapid Solidification Technology and to augment the toughness of the composite by use of SCS-6 filaments as reinforcing fibers.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Materials The matrix material was made by melt spinning appropriate quantities of aluminum and titanium. The molten alloy was

rapidly solidified on a rotating molybdenum wheel. The resultant ribbon was mechanically pulverized. X-ray diffraction techniques were utilized to determine the phases which formed in 1) the melt spun metal ribbon, 2) the consolidated monolithic alloy, and 3) the consolidated composites. Energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) was utilized to determine the distribution of elements within the consolidated monolithic alloy and composites.

The SCS-6 fibers used in this study were purchased from Textron Specialty Materials. The SCS-6 fibers coated with TiB_2 were provided by NASA Langley Research Center.

2.2 Processing Titanium cans were filled with Al_3Ti powder, Al_3Ti powder with SCS-6 fibers, and Al_3Ti powder with TiB_2 coated SCS-6 fibers. The cans were cold pressed to 60-70% density. They were then heated to $400^\circ C$ for 1 hour, hot evacuated, and sealed. The composites were consolidated by hot isostatic pressing (HIP). The composites were HIP'ed at $1100^\circ C$ and 172 MPa for 4 hours.

2.3 Metallography After consolidation the titanium can was removed from the sample. The consolidated alloy and composite were cut by electron discharge machining (EDM). Cross sections perpendicular to the fiber surface were prepared by diamond polishing. The composites were examined by optical microscopy and scanning electron microscopy.

2.4 Hardness Microhardness measurements were taken on the matrix, fiber, and interphase regions. A Tukon microhardness indenter with a 0.5 kg load was used.

3. RESULTS

The matrix material consisted of primarily Al_3Ti . However, X-ray results confirmed the presence of some residual aluminum in the alloy. The residual aluminum was present in the melt spun ribbon, the monolithic alloy, and the matrix material of the composite after consolidation. The microstructure of the Al_3Ti was the same in the consolidated monolithic alloy and the composite. The grains varied in size and were irregularly shaped in both the monolithic alloy and the composite (Figure 1).

After consolidation, the uncoated SCS-6 fibers were not detectable in the Al_3Ti matrix. This indicated that extensive reaction occurred between the uncoated SCS-6 fiber and the matrix at the processing conditions which were used i.e., ($1100^\circ C$ and 172 MPa for 4 hours).

The SCS-6 fibers which were coated with TiB_2 also reacted extensively. However, there were still remains of what once was a SiC fiber. It appears that the SiC fibers reacted with the liquid aluminum (Figure 2a). The remaining fiber region has a high concentration of titanium and silicon. This region is approximately 200 μm diameter. The area adjacent to this region is aluminum rich.

The microhardness measurements confirm these observations. The area adjacent to the fiber region is very soft. The matrix region is the hardest component; it is the same as that of the monolithic alloy. The hardness of the fiber region is softer than that of the matrix. The hardness results are given in Table I and Figure 2b.

TABLE I. Hardness Results

Region	Chemical Composition EDS & X-Ray Results	Microhardness (Vickers) D.P.H
Monolithic Alloy	$Al_3Ti + Al$	520
Composite Matrix	$Al_3Ti + Al$	511
Adjacent to Fiber	Al	76
Fiber Region	Ti, Si, - Al	325

4. DISCUSSION

It appears that the presence of residual aluminum in the Al_3Ti matrix material is severely detrimental. Extensive reaction between elemental aluminum in the matrix and the SiC fibers occurred during hot isostatic processing. Elemental aluminum melts at 660°C. Silicon is completely miscible in liquid aluminum at the processing temperature i.e., 1100°C. As a result, the liquid aluminum reacted profusely with the SiC fibers; the uncoated SCS-6 fibers were completely dissolved.

The TiB_2 coated fibers behaved somewhat differently. Although the fibers eventually reacted with the matrix, the presence of the TiB_2 coating inhibited the dissolution reaction. Both the aluminum and titanium did, however, react with the silicon carbide fibers. The remaining fiber region contained primarily titanium and silicon. Small traces of aluminum were also detected in the remaining fiber. This is consistent with studies showing that TiB_2 is effective in slowing down the interdiffusion

of titanium and silicon carbide at annealing temperatures of approximately 800°C. (7)

There have been extensive studies of the compatibility of SCS-6 fibers in the TiAl and Ti₃Al systems. (8-10) Fiber matrix reaction products which have been identified in these composites include a variety of titanium silicides, titanium carbides, aluminum silicides, and aluminum carbides. Several examples of reaction products are (Ti,Nb)C, Al(Ti,Nb)₃C, and (TiNb)₅(Si,Al)₃. (11) The activity of Ti is lower in Al₃Ti than in either TiAl or Ti₃Al (Figure 3). Therefore, it was expected that the reaction between SiC fibers and an Al₃Ti matrix would be less severe than in either the TiAl or Ti₃Al matrices. However, in this study the presence of residual aluminum in the Al₃Ti matrix caused extensive reaction between the SiC fibers and the matrix.

It is important to note, that when rapidly solidifying Al₃Ti it is preferable to ensure that the alloy is either exactly a line compound or slightly titanium rich. Although Al₃Ti is usually depicted as a line compound, there has been some recent information (12) that there may actually be a narrow range of solubility in this region of the phase diagram. In this study the presence of excess aluminum was found to be detrimental. It is possible that these composites could be successfully consolidated if the matrix material was stoichiometric Al₃Ti. This would prevent the extensive reaction between the liquid aluminum and SiC fibers. The extent of reaction between SiC fibers and a single phase Al₃Ti matrix material remains to be determined.

5. CONCLUSIONS

- 1) Rapid solidification of Al₃Ti requires careful control of the composition in order to avoid excess aluminum in the alloy.
- 2) A two phase matrix of Al₃Ti and residual aluminum is not compatible with SCS-6 fibers or SCS-6 fibers coated with Ti₂B. The liquid aluminum reacts readily with TiB₂ and SiC. However, it appears to react less extensively with TiB₂ coated fibers.
- 3) In an Al₃Ti/Al matrix composite with TiB₂ coated SCS-6 fibers titanium diffuses readily into the SiC fiber leaving behind an aluminum rich interphase region surrounding the fiber.

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8. BIOGRAPHIES

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FIGURE 1. Optical metallograph of the microstructure of the composite matrix material.

a)

b)

FIGURE 2. a) SEM micrograph of Al_3Ti-Al/TiB_2 coated SCS-6 composite showing cross section of remaining fiber and surrounding matrix.

b) Diagram depicting the average microhardness values for each region of the composite after consolidation. Vickers (V.P.H.)

FIGURE 3. Schematic showing the activity of titanium throughout the Al-Ti binary phase diagram.

